

Abstract No. 01**On-farm evaluation of the performance of BWMRI released wheat varieties over local varieties****Hossain MM***, Islam T, Mamun MAA, Mandal MSN, Bazzaz MM*Bangladesh Wheat and Maize Research Institute, Nashipur, Dianjpur-5200*

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Abstract The on-farm experiment was executed in three upazilas: Haripur, Baliadangi, and Ranishankoil, located in the Indian border areas Thakurgaon district during the Rabi 2023–24 season. The aim was to assess the feasibility of BWMRI released new wheat varieties over the local varieties. A total of seven varieties (BWMRI Gom 1, BWMRI Gom 2, BWMRI Gom 3, BWMRI Gom 4, BARI Gom 30, BARI Gom 32, and BARI Gom 33) were evaluated against a local check variety, Sorna/China 3. The experiment was laid out in RCBD with three replications. The unit plot size was 4 m × 5 m. Seeding was done on 21 November 2023 in a continuous pattern at 20 cm line apart. The BWMRI recommended management practices were followed over the farmer's practices. After the data analysis with R software, the highest yield was observed in BWMRI Gom 2 (5.30 t ha⁻¹) and BWMRI Gom 4 (5.10 t ha⁻¹). In contrast, the lowest yield (3.23 t ha⁻¹) was observed in the Sorna/China 3. The yields of BARI Gom30, BARI Gom 32, BARI Gom 33, and BWMRI Gom 1 were comparable, ranging from 4.33 to 4.57 t ha⁻¹. Data revealed that, BWMRI Gom 2 and BWMRI Gom 4 varieties are superior to replace local variety(s) Sorna/China 3 in these areas.

Keywords BWMRI Practice, Wheat, Yield, Replace, Superior**Abstract No. 02****The effect of variety and time of de-topping on the grain and forage yield of maize****Bazzaz MM***, Alam MN, Shakib I, Toma NI, Zihad MAM, Hossain MM*Bangladesh Wheat and Maize Research Institute, Nashipur, Dianjpur-5200*

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Abstract The experiment was conducted at the research field of Bangladesh Wheat and Maize Research Institute, Nashipur, Dianjpur during Rabi season in 2022–23 and 2023–24. The experiment was laid out in RCBD with three replications. The unit plot size was 3m × 3m. Two maize varieties viz., BARI Hybrid Maize 9 and BARI Hybrid Maize 16 were sown on 24 November in 2022 and on 15 November in 2023 with a spacing of 60 cm × 20 cm spacing. Four de-topping treatments viz. D₁ = Control (No de-topping), D₂ = De-topping at 10 days after silking (DAS), D₃ = De-topping at 20 DAS, and D₄ = De-topping at 30 DAS were employed. From two years result, highest grain yield (12.05 t ha⁻¹ in 2022–23 and 11.79 t ha⁻¹ in 2023–24) was obtained in BARI Hybrid Maize 16, de-topped at 30 DAS. On the other hand, the highest green forage yield 9.22 t ha⁻¹ in 2022–23 and 9.17 t ha⁻¹ in 2023–24 was recorded in BARI Hybrid Maize 16, de-topped at 10 DAS and de-topping at 30 DAS recorded considerable amount of forage yield. The highest gross return (3,45,205 Tk. ha⁻¹) and gross margin (2,48,955 Tk. ha⁻¹) were obtained in BARI Hybrid Maize 16, at 30 DAS. So, it can be concluded that de-topping of maize at 30 DAS is economically profitable in respect of both grain and forage yield.

Keywords De-topping, grain yield, forage yield, gross return, gross margin